

Applying Open Access and Open Data to the Archiving of Long-Form Scholarship

A Comparative Analysis of Existing Services Through the Lens of the Copim Open Archiving Criteria

Authors: [Tobias Steiner](#), [Gareth Cole](#), [Jenny Fry](#), [Rupert Gatti](#), Ross Higman, [Paul Stokes](#), [Holly Turpin](#).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19882343>

License: This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Cite as: Steiner, T., Cole, G., Fry, F., Gatti, R., Higman, R., Stokes, P., Steiner, T., & Turpin, H. (2026). *Applying Open Access and Open Data to the Archiving of Long-Form Scholarship: A Comparative Analysis of Existing Services Through the Lens of the Copim Open Archiving Criteria* (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19882343>

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	3
Key Findings.....	4
Comparing services against the Copim Open Archiving Criteria – a matrix.	5
CLOCKSS.....	5
Portico.....	7
Internet Archive.....	8
Zenodo.....	10
Figshare.....	11
Comparative Analysis: A "Dark vs. Open" Dichotomy.....	13
Governance Structure, Sustainability, and Independence.....	14
Integrity and Redundancy.....	16
Summary and Recommendations.....	16
Limitations.....	18
Works Cited.....	18

Introduction

As a recent study by Bell et. al. (2026) has indicated, the long-term preservation of the digital scholarly long-form (e.g. monographs, edited collections, theses, reports, etc.) holds multifaceted challenges. This holds particularly true in the context of preserving open access long-form scholarly output. Small-to-medium-sized institutional as well as independent, scholar-led presses make up much of the “long tail” of publishers without an active preservation policy in place, putting their significant contributions to the scholarly record at risk. As a recent study dissecting the archiving and preservation status of open access books suggests, there is “reason for concern for the long tail of OA books distributed at thousands of different web domains as these include volatile cloud storage or sometimes no longer contained the files at all” (Laakso, 2023).

And while larger publishers usually have existing agreements with digital preservation services such as CLOCKSS and Portico in place, smaller presses often languish without financial or institutional support, while simultaneously facing challenges when it comes to the availability of technical expertise and staff resources (Barnes et al. 2022).

Furthermore, many of the established archiving solutions have been developed with a “traditional”, closed-access model of publication in mind. In contrast, open access titles, as per their definition, are made available openly on the web. As the foundational Budapest Open Access Initiative has posited in 2002:

By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. The only constraint on reproduction and distribution, and the only role for copyright in this domain, should be to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly acknowledged and cited. (Chan et. al., 2022)

The remit of open access, then, poses new challenges to archiving and preservation workflows. Higman et al. (2025) have recently identified distinct factors when considering fully open access publishing outputs and practices. The team outlined a set of criteria that are considered essential to any approach to archiving that aims to preserve the open nature of the content to be preserved. This set of criteria, now titled Copim Open Archiving Criteria (Cole et. al. 2026), include the following:

- Content remains accessible in an open way
- Metadata remains accessible openly
- Archiving processes remain transparent and are verifiable in an open way:
- Adherence to Accepted Good Practice in Digital Archiving Operations

In addition, desirable features of such an open approach to archiving include support for the archival of supplementary and web-based materials, well-defined content removal policies, the provision of usage statistics, and independence from private or government-controlled entities.

The report at hand takes these open archiving criteria as a starting point, and uses the defined set as the basis of a comprehensive analysis of five prominent solutions commonly used for archiving of digital content, including books: CLOCKSS, Portico, the Internet Archive, Zenodo, and Figshare. The analysis is structured around the above-outlined eight key criteria, and ranges from questions of content accessibility and technical reliability to organisational independence and sustainability. The goal of this analysis is to provide an informed overview that moves beyond a simple feature comparison, and towards a more nuanced understanding of each solution's underlying philosophy, governance model, and strategic value proposition.

Key Findings

The central finding of this analysis is the existence of a fundamental philosophical dichotomy within the digital preservation landscape. It is proposed here to categorise the solutions into two distinct models: "dark archives" and "openly accessible repositories."

Dark archives such as CLOCKSS or Portico do not represent repositories in the regular understanding of the term, as they do not provide immediate access to content. Rather, they constitute insurance policies for scholarly content that is not commonly made accessible in an open way, and their operational logic correspondingly encapsulates a closed-access regime. Their core mission is to preserve content in a restricted state, releasing it to the public only if a catastrophic "trigger event" (e.g., a publisher ceasing operations) occurs. This model, supported by consortia of publishers and libraries, is designed to protect publishers' business models while ensuring the long-term upkeep of the scholarly content produced by those publishers.

In contrast, open repositories such as the Internet Archive, Zenodo, Figshare, or many of the institutional repositories listed in COAR's International Repository Directory ([IRD](#)) tend to prioritise immediate and universal access to knowledge. Particularly large-scale generalist repositories such as the Internet Archive and Zenodo have a dedicated mission to disseminate content as widely as possible, providing a public good by making research outputs, cultural artifacts, and web history openly available upon deposit. It seems noteworthy that many of those repositories also have the capability of limiting access to research outputs where needed.

On both sides of this spectrum, governance and funding models can vary widely, ranging from non-profit foundations to intergovernmental organisations and fully for-profit entities. The following sections will provide more detailed insights into different instantiations by

comparing key stakeholder's approaches through the perspective of the open archiving principles presented above.

Comparing services against the Copim Open Archiving Criteria - a matrix

The following matrix provides a side-by-side comparison of each archiving solution against the twelve open archiving criteria. This table serves as the central data reference point for the detailed analysis that follows.

2026-04 Archiving Platform Comparison against Open Archiving criteria - final

CLOCKSS

CLOCKSS (short for Controlled LOCKSS) is a US-based 501(c)(3) not-for-profit organisation established between scholarly publishers and research libraries. Its mission is to create a geographically distributed dark archive to ensure the long-term survival of web-based scholarly publications for the benefit of the global research community. Operationalising the open-source "Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe" (LOCKSS) distributed model of archiving, CLOCKSS' model is centered on closed preservation, not the provision of immediate access to archived content. The value proposition of CLOCKSS is its role as a failsafe or an insurance policy for publisher's content. Content remains in a "dark" state, inaccessible to users unless a disruptive "trigger event" occurs. Trigger events are defined as e.g. a publisher ceasing operations, or other longer-term catastrophes that mean the publisher is not able to carry forward in its previously-established role (CLOCKSS Primer, 2022).

Within CLOCKSS' operational framework, content is first ingested via servers at Rice, Indiana, and Stanford universities, where it is verified for identity to establish an authoritative version. This content is then collected by twelve "CLOCKSS nodes", aka. long-term preservation machines at major academic institutions around the world. The core of the system's integrity is a "polling-and-repair mechanism," which enables these peer nodes to continuously audit the content they hold. If content on one node is found to be damaged or incomplete, it is repaired using content from other nodes or from the original ingest servers (CLOCKSS Ingest Pipeline, 2019).

It's safe to say that CLOCKSS excels in terms of adherence to accepted good practice in digital archiving operations, particularly with a view of meeting established standards: It satisfies the criteria for membership within Keepers Registry, and is classified as a certified CoreTrustSeal repository.

CLOCKSS operates with a clear policy regarding content traceability across time. Material is not deleted from the archive. Instead, corrected or retracted versions of articles are added,

preserving a permanent audit trail of the scholarly record (CLOCKSS Collection Development Policy, n.d.).

With a view on sustainability, CLOCKSS highlights its role as a financially secure 501(c)(3) non-profit with a diversified funding stream from hundreds of publishers and libraries, which is governed by a board with equal representation from libraries and publishers. It seems noteworthy here that a good portion of CLOCKSS' Board of Directors is made up of representatives from big commercial publishers, incl. representatives from Elsevier, Wiley, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, and Wolters Kluwer, as well as aggregators such as OCLC. The last independent audit of CLOCKSS, conducted by the Center for Research Libraries was held in 2018 (CRL, 2018).

The CLOCKSS model necessitates a particular stance on accessibility. As a dark archive, content is not openly available upon deposit, and there is no public-facing mechanism for tracking content-level usage statistics. The organisation's privacy policy mentions the collection of aggregated and usage data from its website, but not from the archived content itself. CLOCKSS also supports the preservation of associated materials, including datasets, images, and supplementary files, and has clear guidelines for crawling web content via static URIs. Before CLOCKSS triggers content for release into open access, it must be approved by the Board. It is worth noting that over time, multiple external sources have highlighted issues with CLOCKSS' actioning of the release workflow for "triggered" content that is stored in its holdings. For more on this, see e.g. the recent discussion around the disappearance and prolonged inaccessibility of the *Heterocycles* journal (Mounce, 2024a; Mounce, 2024b), which had subsequently been resolved.

As these cases show, the effectiveness of CLOCKSS is rooted in a fundamental paradox: its trustworthiness as a preservation solution is directly related to its obscurity as a repository. This model addresses a critical business requirement for "traditional" scholarly publishers of closed-access works. Such publishers' primary revenue stream is often tied to selling access to their intellectual property (either to an individual, or to institutions). A preservation service that made content immediately public upon deposit would directly threaten this business model, making collaboration with such a service undesirable. CLOCKSS circumvents this problem by operating as a dark archive. Its value proposition to publishers is the assurance that access to their content will remain exclusive until a pre-defined trigger event occurs, at which point the preservation service turns into a public access service. This model requires a foundation of trust that enables particularly "traditional" publishers to confidently commit their content to a third-party archive. The absence of public-facing usage statistics for the content is not a deficiency but a direct, causal effect of this particular trust-building model rooted in "traditional", closed-source publishing ; a service with no public usage has no usage to report. This strategic choice enables CLOCKSS to secure the buy-in necessary to fulfill its core mission of safeguarding the scholarly record for the long term particularly for closed-access titles.

Portico

Portico, a digital preservation service of the 501(c)(3) Ithaka Harbors, Inc. (short: ITHAKA), operates as one of the largest digital academic archives in the world. Portico® and ITHAKA® are registered trademarks of ITHAKA. Portico's mission is to work with libraries and publishers to preserve their collections of e-journals, e-books, and other scholarly content in a "dark" archive, ensuring long-term access to the scholarly record. The primary goal is to protect the investments of its participating libraries and publishers in electronic content.

Portico's preservation policies are composed with the advice and guidance of publishing and library communities, and it regularly consults with major national libraries such as the Library of Congress and the British Library. Similar to CLOCKSS, Portico also is a member of the international Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC). According to Portico's website, their processes are informed by community standards such as the Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS), Metadata Encoding & Transmission Standard (METS), and Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies (PREMIS) (Why Portico, n.d.).

Similar to CLOCKSS, Portico's main service is the provision of a dark archive solution. Portico preserves a wide variety of content types, including e-journals, e-books, and digital collections, as well as audio and video content. Its content is not openly accessible upon deposit, and content is commonly released only to participating member libraries and their communities once a "trigger event" occurs. Since 2017, the organisation has begun engaging publishers to effectuate an update of their preservation agreements to allow access to their OA content to be opened, in case of a trigger event, not only to Portico members but to anyone around the world (DiFiore, 2017). At the time of writing, zero open access book titles are being listed in Portico's [Triggered Content portal](#) that is commonly used to make triggered content available to either participating members or the general public (in the case of open access content).

Portico has also undergone independent audits held by the Center for Research Libraries (CRL) and following the TRAC audit model. The last publicly-available audit report is dated Jan 10, 2010. The solution satisfies the criteria for membership within Keepers Registry (relevant for journal content), and is aligned with the Open Archival Information System reference model (OAIS, ISO 14721; Giarretta, 2011).

Content archived via Portico is held in perpetuity and is not commonly subject to deletion. Portico's [Content Modification and Removal](#) policy defines the relevant processes involved. The service does not provide real-time usage statistics for its content. However, it can generate manual usage reports for participating libraries upon request. As the 2010 audit noted: "there is no way to independently [emphasis in original, T.S.] verify and monitor the presence and integrity of content in a repository like Portico comprehensively or on a meaningful scale. Such verification and monitoring is a challenge inherent in "dark"

archives, which are unable to be accessed for such purposes" (CRL & OCLC, 2010. p7).

In contrast to the geographically-distributed network approach practiced by CLOCKSS, Portico sees itself as a centralised, collaborative repository. To address the need of geographic redundancy, Portico stores what it calls "Online Replica" in New Jersey as well as Texas, and holds both offline and online Replica on a dedicated server hosted by Koninklijke Bibliotheek, the National Library of the Netherlands. A separate complete copy of the original supplied files (pre-processing) are also archived in AWS Glacier (Orphan, 2019).

Portico's sustainability is secured by a diversified funding stream from ca. 1,300 libraries and 1,300 publishers. As the 2010 audit highlighted, "Portico is fiscally dependent upon ITHAKA, and thus its relationship with JSTOR presents both a risk and an opportunity. This affiliation with JSTOR might be a deterrent to some publishers' willingness to deposit journal content in the Portico Archive" (CRL & OCLC, 2010. p.8).

A perceived strength of Portico can be seen in its collaborative, social infrastructure. While its technical documentation may not be as explicitly described as that of CLOCKSS, its focus on community guidance and institutional partnerships appears to be a crucial element of its value proposition. Portico recognises that no single archive can preserve the entire scholarly landscape, and it positions itself as a key collaborative hub within a larger preservation ecosystem. This collaborative model proposes to build trust by ensuring that its policies and processes are continuously refined through expert consultation. Portico's close ties to ITHAKA, and its integrated offer for participating libraries to share their special collections via the JSTOR digital discovery platform while also taking care of preservation via Portico remains a unique service model that promises to "future-proof" libraries' digital content.

Internet Archive

The Internet Archive is a non-profit organisation and registered library with a mission of "Universal Access to All Knowledge". This mission stands in notable contrast to the dark archive model of CLOCKSS and Portico. The Internet Archive functions as a public digital library, providing free and immediate access to a vast collection of digitised media, including websites, software, music, and print materials. Its most well-known service, the [Wayback Machine](#), archives hundreds of billions of web pages and their associated content. The organisation's model is predicated on the public benefit of open access, making it a different class of preservation solution.

The organisation is an independent 501(c)(3) non-profit, and its Board of Directors consists of long-term librarian advocates of open knowledge. The lack of direct influence from commercial publishers seems notable in this context, and has helped to position the Internet Archive as an entity free from direct private or government influence. The organisation's sustainability relies on a combination of individual donations and grants

from foundations. To ensure long-term reliability and resiliency, the Internet Archive has built a robust, geographically redundant infrastructure. It operates six primary data centers across three countries, including a full, second live copy in a Canadian data center (Mills, 2022). The Internet Archive is a congressionally designated depository for US Government documents. Public access to the government documents collection is guaranteed by public law (Title 44 United States Code).

The Internet Archive organisation excels at archiving a broad range of content types. Its web crawlers can capture HTML, CSS, JavaScript, images, and various other files. Next to its core service, Internet Archive helps to run three specialised preservation services: via the [Archive-It](#) program enables partner institutions to archive targeted collections of web content, and with [Vault](#), institutions can more flexibly customise a repository or preservation approach to their individual needs. [ARCH](#) (Archives Research Compute Hub) is the Internet Archive's research and data processing service and platform supporting users to build, analyse and study large digital collections computationally and create datasets and data visualizations. While the Internet Archive satisfies criteria for membership within Keepers Registry, it is not formally certified against ISO 16363, TRAC, or CoreTrustSeal. It might be argued, though, that its operational model reflects many of the core principles of trusted digital repositories.

As an openly accessible repository, the Internet Archive's policies are shaped to facilitate public use and engagement. All content on the platform, whether uploaded by users or collected by its web crawlers, is intended for free access, forever. (Internet Archive, 2023) All metadata is openly available and can be accessed via a dedicated API (Kaplan, 2013). The Internet Archive has a strong policy on content removal, which is a major point of differentiation from the dark archives. Content can be removed for copyright infringement, and repeat infringers may have their accounts terminated. The organisation also retroactively honors robots.txt files, which can make previously archived content unavailable.

The Internet Archive's commitment to open access is also reflected in its approach to usage statistics. It tracks and shares "views" and "downloads" for individual items and collections, with metrics updated daily and monthly.

The organisation's mission of universal access, while noble, is not without its challenges. The Internet Archive's public-facing nature and its primary location in the United States subject it to legal and political pressures that do not typically affect dark archives that are operating under private contracts and cater to a more selective customer base. A clear example of this is the lawsuit over its Controlled Digital Lending (CDL) program, which resulted in a legal ruling that barred the organisation from digitally lending books for which electronic copies are on sale ([Hachette v. Internet Archive](#)). This kind of legal action, compounded by potential political instability, creates a strategic risk that is fundamentally different from the risks faced by a private consortium. The decision to create a full, second live copy of the archive in a Canadian data center (Mills, 2022) is a direct, causal

consequence of this legal and political landscape. This move can be understood as a strategic manoeuvre to protect the collection from potential jurisdictional or political threats in the United States, an acknowledgment that even the most robust technical infrastructure is vulnerable to non-technical, external risks. This situation highlights a critical difference: a public-facing archive, by its very nature, must navigate a complex legal and political environment.

Zenodo

Zenodo is a multi-disciplinary, open-access repository developed by the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN) as part of the OpenAIRE project. Its mission is to provide a dependable home for the "long-tail" of research, enabling researchers to share and preserve small research outputs, data, and software that might not be suitable for existing institutional or subject-based repositories. Zenodo's repository, which is based on the [Invenio](#) open-source software stack, is free to use (upload and access), with the explicit goal of making the sharing, curation, and publication of data and software easily available for all researchers worldwide.

Zenodo's operations are deeply aligned with the principles of open science and FAIR data. Content can be made available under closed, open, or embargoed access. Files deposited under closed access are protected against unauthorised access at all levels. For closed access deposits, Zenodo notes that "zenodo.org users will not be able to access the files you uploaded. The files are however stored unencrypted and may be viewed by Zenodo operational staff under specific conditions. This means that "closed access" on Zenodo is not suitable for secret or confidential data" (Zenodo Infrastructure, n.d.).

The platform is built to support a wide range of content types and is integrated with GitHub for simplified software preservation. Zenodo has clearly stated policies for content removal, including spam, copyright infringement, and scientific misconduct. It also tracks and shares detailed usage statistics, including visits and downloads, through a public API. The platform complies with recognised industry standards such as COUNTER and Make Data Count, ensuring that its metrics are comparable with other repositories (Zenodo FAQ: Statistics, n.d.).

Following open data principles, all metadata created by Zenodo is released under a CC0 dedication to maximise easy re-use. The organisation makes that public data freely available for harvesting by third parties via standard protocols such as OAI-PMH. The platform has robust, openly verifiable processes for content integrity. Every file is stored with two independent MD5 checksums, and files are "regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant". The platform supports version control for data files, ensuring that any changes are tracked and that previous versions are preserved (Zenodo General Policies, n.d.). Zenodo is a certified CoreTrustSeal repository, and is aligned with OAIS (ISO 14721).

Zenodo's sustainability is explicitly tied to CERN's experimental program, which is projected to last for at least the next 20 years. In the event of closure, Zenodo states it will make "best efforts to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories" (Zenodo General Policies, n.d.). The repository benefits from a high degree of geographic redundancy, with all data stored in CERN Data Centres and replicated in two distinct locations, Geneva and Budapest. Financial support is provided via a host of funding agencies, incl. through the European Commission via a number of OpenAIRE projects, the US National Institutes of Health (NIH), Arcadia Fund, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, The Navigation Fund, and via donations collected through the CERN & Society Foundation.

Zenodo's mission is deeply rooted in the open science movement, providing a critical service for researchers who lack institutional repositories or who produce diverse digital artifacts. Zenodo's organisational structure might be seen by some as introducing a unique dependency: Zenodo is not run by an independent consortium, it is a service of CERN, which is an intergovernmental organisation.

It seems noteworthy that in that capacity, CERN enjoys "certain privileges and immunities, including e.g. immunity from jurisdiction of the national courts to ensure [CERN's] independence from individual Member States" (Zenodo Infrastructure, n.d.). This independence can well be seen as a unique asset, as it prioritises the infrastructure's impartiality – the importance of which, in light of the spread of authoritarian tendencies on the level of nation-states across the globe, can not be overstated.

Zenodo's reliance on an institutional parent, while providing a stable, large-scale infrastructure, means that Zenodo's long-term viability is linked to the institutional policies, funding, and mission of CERN. It also is noteworthy that CERN, as the operating institution, has always highlighted its role as a safe haven for research. The role, or influence, of commercial entities in this space has been clearly defined by Tim Smith, member of Zenodo's Steering Committee:

"For-profits can be involved in parts of the research lifecycle, but they should never be allowed to own any part of it. They can facilitate, but they cannot be the arbiter or gatekeeper." (quoted in Franck, 2019)

While the current commitment is strong, the underlying model carries a different type of risk than a member-governed consortium. A change in institutional priorities or a shift in funding could have significant, long-term implications for the repository's future. The "best efforts" succession plan in case of closure, while prudent, is not the same as a permanent, legally-binding contract with a dedicated preservation organisation.

Figshare

Figshare is a web-based, for-profit service with the mission to improve the dissemination and discoverability of all scholarly research outputs. The Figshare platform is an

open-access repository for researchers to preserve and share a wide variety of research outputs, from figures and datasets to videos and code. A critical element of its identity is its organisational structure: Figshare is a service by Digital Science, a for-profit company and subsidiary of Springer Nature. This corporate-owned model is a key differentiator from all the other non-profit solutions considered in this comparison.

Figshare's service is designed to be highly accessible and user-friendly, and consists of two tiers: Figshare's repository solution is available as a bespoke Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) implementation to clients such as Higher Education Institutions. Next to that, its free platform, figshare.com, can be used by researchers worldwide, with content being openly accessible upon deposit, and all metadata being published under a CC0 dedication.

“Our free service only offers CC BY and CC0 as options. We believe that nudging our users in this direction – it's ‘the price’ they pay – is essential to making research as open as possible.” Mark Hahnel, CEO of Figshare, in Franck, 2019.

Figshare also provides the option of enabling the declaration of access embargoes, under which a deposit's metadata will be publicly accessible, but its content remains hidden (Figshare Embargoes and restricted access publishing, n.d.). The platform supports version control for both files and metadata, with previous versions remaining accessible on an item's page. Content integrity is ensured through MD5 integrity checks performed at the time of file upload. Figshare also tracks and displays a comprehensive suite of usage statistics, including views, downloads, citations, and Altmetrics, and is compliant with industry standards like Make Data Count and COUNTER (Figshare Usage Metrics and Statistics, n.d.).

Figshare's reliability and sustainability are tied to its commercial business model and its use of a commercial cloud provider. The platform is hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS) S3, and refers to the Amazon S3 Service Level Agreement for specifics on reliability. Currently, Figshare relies on a region-specific provision of S3,, which is designed to sustain the concurrent loss of data in two facilities. To increase redundancy, Figshare “is exploring additional AWS Cross Region Replication options” to enable recovery from an AWS EU region failure (Figshare Policies, n.d.). With a view on established good archival practice, Figshare [highlights its compliance](#) with OSTP and NIH “Desirable Characteristics for Data Repositories”. While Figshare's hosting provider, Amazon Web Services, itself is not certified against ISO 16363, TRAC, or CoreTrustSeal, it might be argued that it delivers the core technical controls required for bit-level preservation and secure archival storage.

Figshare's content removal policies are clearly stated. The platform maintains the right to remove content that violates its Terms of Acceptable Use, such as copyrighted material, promotional content, or content that has already been published with a DOI. The platform is built to handle a wide variety of associated materials, including supplemental information provided by publishers.

Figshare's reliance on a commercial cloud provider and its corporate ownership by a major

academic publisher represent a complex blend of advantages and risks. The use of a platform like AWS grants Figshare immense technical flexibility, scalability, and a high degree of data durability. However, its underlying for-profit nature introduces a different kind of long-term risk. Figshare's primary commitment is ultimately to its shareholders within the Digital Science / Holtzbrinck Publishing Group ecosystem. This creates an explicit financial incentive to prioritise a short-to-mid-term business logic of profit maximisation over a longer-term community focus to ensure the upkeep of preservation infrastructure.

While Figshare's ten-year SLA (Figshare User Guide, n.d.) is a strong commitment, it is not the same as the multi-generational or in-perpetuity preservation missions of the non-profit solutions presented here. This suggests that for-profit repositories, while technically advanced and highly functional, may not be perceived as neutral, "forever" solutions for institutions seeking to preserve the scholarly record without commercial influence. The fundamental nature of a for-profit enterprise means its business model could change over time to meet its prime directive of market demands – a variable that is arguably either absent in, or at least less foregrounded, in the non-profit consortial models represented by the other solutions investigated here.

Figshare makes an explicit note to highlight that it does not offer long-term preservation options for clients of its hosted service. Instead, it provides integrations to enable its customers to link the relevant Figshare instance with existing third-party preservation solutions (Figshare Security, Stability, and ISO27001 Certification, n.d.; Cotera et. al., 2023).

Comparative Analysis: A "Dark vs. Open" Dichotomy

The most profound distinction among the repository/archiving solutions is their approach to content accessibility. This is not merely a feature difference; it is a fundamental choice that impacts every other criterion.

Dark archives like CLOCKSS and Portico operate on what often is labeled as a "trust-based" model. Their value proposition to publishers is the guarantee that copyrighted, subscription-based content will not be made openly available prior to the occurrence of a catastrophic trigger event. This model effectively acts as a business-enabling feature, building trust particularly with commercial publishers of closed-access titles by safeguarding their primary revenue model. Consequently, for these solutions, public-facing metadata, public access to content, and real-time usage statistics are either non-existent or restricted to participating members with audit privileges. Their purpose is to insure content against loss.

In contrast, the open repositories considered here (Internet Archive, Zenodo, Figshare) operate on a "utility-based" model. Their mission is to maximise discoverability, accessibility, and impact of content in the spirit of open access and, more broadly, open scholarship. This is a model built for the public, providing an enormous social good by

making research and cultural artifacts freely available. For these solutions, openly accessible content and robust usage metrics are core features that demonstrate their value and utility. Their purpose is to help facilitate immediate and consistent access to, and (re-)use of, openly-licensed content.

A strategic decision-maker must weigh these two competing values. Is the goal to insure content against the risk of disappearance (a dark archive) against the backdrop of a commercial, closed-source business model that seeks to project artificial scarcity by hiding digital content behind paywalls? Or is it to maximise a publisher’s immediate use and impact? For institutional libraries, a comprehensive strategy often involves a partnership with both types of solutions: a dark archive for licensed collections and an open repository for institutional and open-access data.

Governance Structure, Sustainability, and Independence

The long-term viability of a digital archive is not solely a technical matter but is inextricably linked to its governance and business model. Each solution under review has a different approach to fund its operations through different mechanisms, each of which carry distinct risks. The following table compares these models.

Platform	Funding Model	Legal Status	Governance Structure	Perceived Independence
CLOCKSS	Fees sourced from participating publishers and libraries	Non-profit (501(c)(3))	Board with equal representation from libraries and commercial publishers	Answers to its community board. Potential risks: 1) The legal entity is subject to its country of origin's jurisdiction (USA). 2) The strong representation of large commercial publishers.
Portico	Fees sourced from participating libraries and publishers	Service provided by non-profit (501(c)(3) ITHAKA)	Board of Trustees via ITHAKA, plus Portico Advisory Board consisting of university presidents, librarians, publishers, and faculty members Collaborative model	Operates in close collaboration with community stakeholders. Potential risk: 1) The legal entity is subject to its country of origin's jurisdiction (USA) 2) Close ties to its sibling platform JSTOR, and

			with advice and guidance from its university, library, and publishing constituents	parent company ITHAKA – both of which may influence the service's direction.
Internet Archive	Donations and grants from individuals and foundations	Non-profit (501(c)(3))	Board of Directors comprised of advocates of open scholarship	A non-profit governed by a board of librarians. Potential risk: The legal entity is subject to its country of origin's jurisdiction (USA)
Zenodo	Institutional funding from CERN and the EU, via OpenAIRE.	Non-profit (a service of CERN)	A service of CERN, an intergovernmental research organisation. Steering Board comprising open infrastructure experts from CERN.	Zenodo's existence and governance are tied to its host institution CERN, an intergovernmental research body with a special legislative constitution that ensures institutional independence from external forces.
Figshare	For-profit, revenue based on provision of commercial services and licenses	For-profit (a subsidiary of Springer Nature)	Corporate ownership by its parent company	Figshare is a for-profit entity owned by a major publishing conglomerate, and bound by its governance structure.

CLOCKSS and Portico are member-based services that cater primarily to their primary stakeholders. For Zenodo, it is an institutional commitment from a large intergovernmental research body, CERN. For Figshare, it is commercial viability within a corporate ecosystem. Each model carries a different type of risk. A member-governed consortium like CLOCKSS or Portico is vulnerable to internal politics e.g. from large commercial member entities. An institutional project like Zenodo is dependent on the long-term mission and funding of its host institution. A for-profit model like Figshare's is subject to market competition, business strategy shifts, and the pressures of corporate ownership. When considering the perceived independence of each provider, an understanding of these risks and dependencies seems highly pertinent.

Integrity and Redundancy

The analysis of technical integrity and geographic redundancy reveals a critical truth: technology can only be as reliable as its custodian. While all solutions claim a high degree of technical robustness, the mechanisms and underlying assumptions differ.

CLOCKSS is proud of its unique, custom-built infrastructure of 12 distributed LOCKSS nodes that continuously "poll and repair" content, a mechanism designed specifically for multi-generational digital preservation, which in principle represents a robust approach to long-term preservation technology. Both CLOCKSS and Portico highlight that their systems have successfully been audited. Publicly available records show that these audits have last taken place in 2010 (Portico), and in 2018 (CLOCKSS).

In contrast, Figshare relies on the commercial Service Level Agreements (SLAs) of a third-party cloud provider, Amazon Web Services (AWS). While AWS provides a high degree of durability and redundancy, the service does not *per se* constitute a long-term archiving solution.¹

Zenodo uses the institutional data centres of CERN and, similar to Figshare, relies on a MD5 checksum-based verification process and replication in one additional geographically-different location.

In a similar vein, and as a direct response to mounting legal and political pressures within the United States (Mills, 2022), the Internet Archive decided to establish a full, second live copy of its entire collection in a Canadian data centre. This makes the case of the Internet Archive an apt demonstration of looming vulnerabilities that extend beyond mere technical factors.

Summary and Recommendations

As has been shown, the digital archiving solutions examined in this report are not interchangeable. They represent distinct philosophies, business models, and risk profiles.

CLOCKSS and Portico are community-governed, non-profit closed dark archives that prioritise the preservation of the scholarly record for future access while simultaneously acting as an insurance policy for publishers and libraries that publish and curate paywalled content for their clients. Their offer is the provision of detailed, audited processes – a claim that some may find difficult to verify from an external or even public perspective. Both solutions have been established with a closed-access, commercial approach to publishing in mind. The influence of the legacy, closed-access publishing sector becomes particularly

¹ It is worth noting that Amazon also offers long-term data archiving-grade storage classes such as [Glacier](#) (which is being used by e.g. Portico and Thoth). There is no explicit mention of Glacier in Figshare's Service Level Agreement with AWS, though.

noteworthy in the case of CLOCKSS: the non-profit very much stresses the importance of trust, and prides itself as working with “the community” – but when we consider that the majority of publisher representatives on the institution’s Board is drawn from the ranks of large commercial publishers, one might be drawn to ask which “community” one is being asked to trust here. Cases such as the Heterocycles journal disappearance (Mounce, 2024a; Mounce, 2024b), and the fact that zero OA titles have been released under CLOCKSS’ stewardship may raise further questions as to exactly which parts of its community the non-profit is actually serving. In a similar fashion, with Portico, it is worth remembering that the archiving solution has been established to serve the JSTOR community of subscribers. And while JSTOR nowadays has an open access component in its service portfolio, the service itself had been established with a traditional, content-subscription-based model in mind.

On the other side of the spectrum, we locate the Internet Archive, Zenodo, and Figshare – open repositories that prioritise the immediate dissemination of knowledge. The Internet Archive serves as a public library and archive for a broad spectrum of cultural heritage. Zenodo is an institutional repository for the “long-tail” of research data, with its sustainability and integrity ensured by CERN policies. Figshare is a for-profit, corporate-owned entity that provides a commercial, open access-amenable solution with a high degree of technical agility through its use of a third-party cloud provider.

With a particular view on the solutions’ adherence to accepted Good Practice in Digital Archiving Operations, Amazon S3 provides best-in-class technical durability and integrity controls but lacks repository-level governance, preservation functions, and relevant accreditation from established preservation communities. The Internet Archive implements large-scale archival operations aligned with many OAIS principles but does not hold formal trusted repository certification and exhibits variability in preservation planning. Zenodo, by contrast, is CoreTrustSeal certified and demonstrates structured governance, metadata management, and repository practices consistent with accepted standards for trustworthy digital repositories, though with more limited depth in active preservation planning compared to fully ISO 16363-certified systems.

Portico and CLOCKSS represent fully realised digital preservation services aligned with trusted repository standards, with Portico emphasising active preservation planning and CLOCKSS prioritising distributed resilience. Zenodo, as a CoreTrustSeal-certified repository, provides a baseline level of trusted repository functionality focused on persistent access and metadata quality. The Internet Archive demonstrates large-scale archival capabilities and alignment with many OAIS principles but lacks formal certification and consistent preservation planning. That said, the Internet Archive also is a member of the journal-focused Keepers’ Registry, and a designated federal depository library (Freeland, 2025). Figshare primarily functions as a research data publishing and dissemination platform, offering persistence and metadata management but relying on its underlying infrastructure and institutional policies for long-term preservation, and therefore does not

independently meet trusted digital repository criteria.

All in all, and with a colourful variety of available options to choose from, our review concludes that configurations of stewardship and policy play a key role in preserving open access long-form scholarship. As has been shown, the reviewed solutions are split into two underlying logics: that of dark archives (e.g., CLOCKSS, Portico) that provide audited, insurance-style closed preservation under what some might perceive as vaguely-defined governance terms, and open repositories (e.g., Internet Archive, Zenodo, Figshare) that prioritise immediate access, transparency and reuse.

In conclusion, it seems pertinent to highlight that none of the models reviewed here fully satisfy the open archiving principles. Looking through the comparative dataset, a combination of any two of either one of the dark archives and one of the open repository services, or two open repositories would help to substitute any remaining gaps.

With a view on the needs of small publishers, the availability of free and open repositories means there exists a viable and easily implementable pathway to ensure a press' publications are being archived. That said, any approach seeking to align transparent governance with appropriate technical safeguards and sustainable funding that ensure that the archiving workflows applied explicitly focus on a preservation of the distinct openness characteristics of the content to be archived appear to be preferable to locking content away.

From the approaches discussed here, solutions such as those of Zenodo or the Internet Archive which combine technical excellence with a community-driven, robust governance model that explicitly highlights the benefits of public access and can withstand geopolitical and economic shocks seem to be well-aligned with the open archiving principles.

It thus seems in the best interest of libraries, funders and publishing communities aligned with equitable approaches to open access publishing (e.g. Diamond OA) to invest in such community-governed open infrastructures that underwrite sustainable models of stewardship to safeguard the future of open access long-form scholarship.

Limitations

The scope of this study did not include a wider sweep of preservation services such as those participating in the Global LOCKSS Network, individual non-profit options DuraCloud, Academic Preservation Trust, HathiTrust, Chronopolis, and the Digital Preservation Network, or commercial services available e.g. from ProQuest ExLibris, Preservica, or Arkivum.

Works Cited

- Amazon Web Services, Inc. "Amazon S3 Features." Accessed April 16, 2026.
<https://aws.amazon.com/s3/features/>.
- Amazon Web Services, Inc. "Amazon S3 Service Level Agreement." Accessed April 16, 2026. <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/sla/>.
- Amazon Web Services, Inc. "Secure Storage - Amazon S3 Glacier Storage Classes - AWS." Accessed March 30, 2026. <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/storage-classes/glacier/>.
- Amazon Web Services, Inc. "Amazon S3 Features." Accessed April 16, 2026.
<https://aws.amazon.com/s3/features/>.
- Bahnmaier, Sara, Lorraine Estelle, Evelyn Frangakis, et al. *Digital Preservation Language for Agreements between Libraries and Publishers*. Zenodo, 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7688275>.
- Bell, Graham, David Cirella, Gali Halevi, et al. "Securing the Future of Books: A Collaborative Guide to Preservation." *Learned Publishing* 39, no. 2 (2026): e2047.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.2047>.
- Bryan, Paul C., and Mark Nottingham. *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) Patch*. Request for Comments RFC 6902. Internet Engineering Task Force, 2013.
<https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC6902>.
- Chan, Leslie, Darius Cuplinskas, Michael Eisen, et al. "Budapest Open Access Declaration." Budapest Open Access Initiative, February 14, 2002.
<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>.
- CLOCKSS. "CLOCKSS Collection Development Policy." *CLOCKSS*, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://clockss.org/collection-development-policy/>.
- CLOCKSS. "Extracting Triggered Content." *CLOCKSS Trusted Digital Repository Documents*, September 22, 2025.
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250922171121/https://documents.clockss.org/index.php/CLOCKSS: Extracting Triggered Content>.
- CLOCKSS. "Extracting Triggered Content." *CLOCKSS*, n.d.
<https://documents.clockss.org/index.php/CLOCKSS: Extracting Triggered Content>.
- CLOCKSS. "Home - Digital Preservation Services." Accessed September 21, 2025.

<https://clockss.org/>.

CLOCKSS. "How CLOCKSS Works." *CLOCKSS*, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025.

<https://clockss.org/about/how-clockss-works/>.

CLOCKSS. "Ingest Pipeline -." *CLOCKSS Trusted Digital Repository Documents*. Accessed September 21, 2025.

https://documents.clockss.org/index.php/CLOCKSS: Ingest_Pipeline.

CLOCKSS. "Succession Plan." *CLOCKSS Trusted Digital Repository Documents*, August 14, 2019. https://documents.clockss.org/index.php/CLOCKSS: Succession_Plan.

CLOCKSS. "The CLOCKSS Archive -- Value Proposition." *CLOCKSS*, October 2022.

<https://clockss.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Value-Proposition-Libraries.pdf>.

CLOCKSS. "The CLOCKSS Archive: A Primer." *CLOCKSS*, October 2022.

<https://clockss.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/CLOCKSS-Primer.pdf>.

COAR. "International Repositories Directory (IRD)." *Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)*, n.d. Accessed September 25, 2025.

<https://ird.coar-repositories.org/about?lang=en>.

Cole, G., Gatti, R., Higman, R., Stokes, P., Steiner, T., & Turpin, H. (2026). *Copim Open Archiving Criteria (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19882469>

Collings, Bridget. "About Vault." *Vault Support*, November 30, 2023.

<https://vault-webservices.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/14173270954132-About-Vault>.

Corujo, Luís, Jorge Revez, Carlos Guardado Da Silva, and L. S. Ascensão De Macedo. "Preservation and Digital Repositories: Connections, Possibilities, and Needs." In *Handbook of Trends and Innovations Concerning Library and Information Science*, edited by Barbara Jane Holland. De Gruyter, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783111443003-005>.

Cotera, Maria, Andrew Mckenna-Foster, and Adrian-Tudor Panescu. "A Tale of Two Systems: Research Data Repositories and Digital Preservation." *IFLA WLIC 2023* (Rotterdam), 2023.

CRL. "CLOCKSS Audit Report." *Center for Research Libraries*, November 11, 2018.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20181111191557/http://www.crl.edu/archiving-preservation/digital-archives/certification-and-assessment-digital-repositories/clockss-report/detailed-findings>.

CRL. "Portico | eDesiderata." May 17, 2024.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250922104902/https://edesiderata.crl.edu/resources/portico>.

CRL. "Report on Portico Audit Findings." Center for Research Libraries, January 10, 2010.

CRL, The Center for Research Libraries, and OCLC Online Computer Library Center. "Trustworthy Repositories Audit & Certification: Criteria and Checklist." 2007. <https://www.crl.edu/sites/default/files/2025-01/trac.pdf>.

DiFiore, Ken. "Preserving E-Journals: A Review of the Digital Preservation Landscape." Delta Serials Conference, Arkansas State University, Dean B. Ellis Library, December 2017.

<https://www.portico.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/Digital-Preservation.Delta-Serials-Conference.pdf>.

"DOI Registration." Accessed April 1, 2026. <https://thoth.pub/solutions/doi>.

Eve, Martin Paul. "Digital Scholarly Journals Are Poorly Preserved: A Study of 7 Million Articles." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 12, no. 1 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.31274/jlsc.16288>.

Fenner, Martin, Daniella Lowenberg, Matt Jones, et al. *Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics*. E26505v1. PeerJ Inc., 2018.

<https://doi.org/10.7287/peerj.preprints.26505v1>.

Figshare. "Embargoes and Restricted Access Publishing." *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed March 29, 2026.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/embargoes-and-restricted-access-publishing/>.

Figshare. "Figshare Policies." *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed September 22, 2025.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/figshare-policies/>.

Figshare. "How Is My Data Stored, Is It Secure?" *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed March 29, 2026.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/how-is-my-data-stored-is-it-secure/>.

Figshare. "How Long Will Figshare Host and Retain My Public Research Data For?"

Figshare, n.d. Accessed March 29, 2026.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/how-long-will-figshare-host-and-retain-my-public-research-data-for/>.

Figshare. "Security, Stability, and ISO27001 Certification." *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed March

29, 2026. <https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/security-stability/>.

Figshare. "Usage Metrics and Statistics." *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed March 29, 2026.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/usage-metrics-and-statistics/>.

Franck, Gwen. "Insights into the Economy of Open Scholarship: A Look into Zenodo with Tim Smith, Head of Collaboration, Devices and Applications, CERN/IT."

Preprint, Zenodo, May 15, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.2842593>.

Freeland, Chris. "Letter Designating Internet Archive a Federal Depository Library."

Internet Archive, July 24, 2025.

<http://archive.org/details/padilla-designation-letter-to-gpo-7.24.2025>.

Garcia, Giovanni. "Preserving Open Access and Other At-Risk Scholarly Content."

Portico, October 13, 2020.

<https://www.portico.org/news/preserving-open-access-and-other-at-risk-scholarly-content/>.

"General Policies v1.0." Zenodo, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025.

<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>.

Giaretta, David. "Introduction to OAIS: Concepts and Terminology." In *Advanced Digital Preservation*, edited by David Giaretta. Springer, 2011.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16809-3_3.

Giaretta, David. "OAIS (ISO 14721), ISO 16363 and Others Updated." *PTAB - Primary Trustworthy Digital Repository Authorisation Body Ltd*, March 21, 2025.

<http://www.iso16363.org/oais-iso-14721-iso-16363-and-others-updated/>.

Greenberg, Jonathan, Karen Hanson, and Deb Verhoff. *Guidelines for Preserving New Forms of Scholarship*. 0 ed. New York University, 2021.

<https://doi.org/10.33682/221c-b2xj>.

Hanson, Karen. "Enhancing Services to Preserve New Forms of Scholarship." *Digital Preservation Coalition*, July 22, 2019.

<https://www.dpconline.org/blog/enhancing-services-to-preserve-new-forms-of-scholarship>.

Hanson, Karen. "Portico Content Modification and Deletion Policy v1.4." Portico, September 10, 2025.

https://www.portico.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/Portico_Content_Modification_and_Deletion_Policy_1_4.pdf.

Hanson, Karen. "Portico Replication and Backup Policy, v. 1.3." Portico, July 8, 2023.

Higman, Ross, Gareth Cole, Rupert Gatti, et al. "Putting the 'Open' in 'Thoth Open Archiving Network.'" *Copim*, ahead of print, March 27, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.76e96572>.

"How Figshare.Com Meets the OSTP and NIH 'Desirable Characteristics for Data Repositories.'" *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed April 16, 2026.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/how-figshare-com-meets-the-ostp-and-nih-desirable-characteristics-for-data-repositories/>.

"How Figshare.Com Meets the OSTP and NIH 'Desirable Characteristics for Data Repositories.'" *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025.

<https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/how-figshare-com-meets-the-ostp-and-nih-desirable-characteristics-for-data-repositories/>.

Internet Archive. "Books and Texts." Internet Archive Help Center. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://help.archive.org/help/books-and-texts-tips-troubleshooting/>.

Internet Archive. "Books and Texts – A Basic Guide." Internet Archive Help Center. Accessed September 21, 2025.

<https://help.archive.org/help/books-and-texts-a-basic-guide/>.

Internet Archive. "Browse the Book Shelves with Open Library Explorer." Internet Archive Help Center. Accessed September 21, 2025.

<https://help.archive.org/help/browse-the-book-shelves-with-open-library-explorer/>

.

- Internet Archive. "How Do I Request to Remove Something from Archive.Org?" Internet Archive Help Center, n.d. Accessed March 27, 2026. <https://help.archive.org/help/how-do-i-request-to-remove-something-from-archive-org/>.
- Internet Archive. "Internet Archive Access Policy." Internet Archive Help Center, August 29, 2023. <https://help.archive.org/help/internet-archive-access-policy/>.
- Internet Archive. "Internet Archive Developer Portal." Accessed March 28, 2026. <https://archive.org/developers/index.html>.
- Internet Archive. "Internet Archive Statistics." Internet Archive Help Center, n.d. Accessed March 27, 2026. <https://help.archive.org/help/internet-archive-statistics/>.
- Internet Archive. "Item Metadata API." Internet Archive Developer Portal. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://archive.org/developers/metadata.html>.
- Internet Archive. "Rights." Internet Archive Help Center. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://help.archive.org/help/rights/>.
- Internet Archive. "Statistics." Internet Archive Help Center. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://help.archive.org/help/internet-archive-statistics/>.
- Internet Archive. "Why Are so Many Books Listed as 'Borrow Unavailable' at the Internet Archive." Internet Archive Help Center. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://help.archive.org/help/why-are-so-many-books-listed-as-borrow-unavailable-at-the-internet-archive/>.
- Jones, Shawn M., Herbert Van De Sompel, Harihar Shankar, Martin Klein, Richard Tobin, and Claire Grover. "Scholarly Context Adrift: Three out of Four URI References Lead to Changed Content." *PLOS ONE* 11, no. 12 (2016): e0167475. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0167475>.
- Kahle, Brewster. "How Archive.Org Items Are Structured | Internet Archive Blogs." *Internet Archive Blogs*, March 31, 2011. <https://blog.archive.org/2011/03/31/how-archive-org-items-are-structured/>.
- Kaplan, Jeff. "The Internet Archive Metadata API." *Internet Archive Blogs*, July 4, 2013. <https://blog.archive.org/2013/07/04/metadata-api/>.

- Kirchhoff, Amy, Karen Hanson, Kate Wittenberg, and Sandra Parr. "Succession Policy." Portico, July 8, 2023.
- Kirchhoff, Amy, Kate Wittenberg, Stephanie Orphan, and Ken DiFiore. "Portico E-Book Preservation: Progress Made, Lessons Learned, and Future Directions." CRL Webinar, May 4, 2017.
https://web.archive.org/web/20170710013953/http://www.crl.edu/sites/default/files/event_materials/Portico%20EbookPreservation2017.v2.pdf.
- LOCKSS. "Metadata Database." CLOCKSS, August 14, 2019.
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250922171004/https://documents.clockss.org/index.php/LOCKSS:MetadataDatabase#GraphicalRepresentationofSchema>.
- "LOCKSS: Property Server Operations." CLOCKSS Trusted Digital Repository Documents, August 14, 2019.
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250922171005/https://documents.clockss.org/index.php/LOCKSS:PropertyServerOperations>.
- Mills, Andrea. "Welcome to Canada, Internet Archive." *Internet Archive Canada*, February 15, 2022.
<https://internetarchivecanada.org/2022/02/15/welcome-to-canada-internet-archivel/>.
- Mounce, Ross. "Things We Can Learn from the Ongoing Heterocycles Debacle." *Ross Mounce*, April 11, 2024.
<https://rossmounce.co.uk/2024/04/11/things-we-can-learn-from-the-ongoing-heterocycles-debacle/>.
- Mounce, Ross. "Time to Update the CLOCKSS?" *Ross Mounce*, June 11, 2024.
<https://rossmounce.co.uk/2024/06/11/time-to-update-the-clockss/>.
- NASIG. "Guide to the Keepers Registry." NASIGuide, NASIG, May 29, 2024.
<https://www.nasig.org/Keepers-Registry>.
- NIH. "Selecting a Data Repository | Grants & Funding." National Institute of Health, August 5, 2025.
<https://grants.nih.gov/policy-and-compliance/policy-topics/sharing-policies/dms/selecting-a-data-repository#desirable-characteristics-for-all-data-repositories>.

- Orphan, Stephanie. "What's It All about, Portico? The How, the Now, and Future Directions of Portico Preservation." Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, DigiPres, June 18, 2019.
- Portico. "Facts and Figures." Portico, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://www.portico.org/coverage/facts-and-figures/>.
- Portico. "Governance." *Portico*, n.d. Accessed March 31, 2026. <https://www.portico.org/governance/>.
- Portico. "Preservation Step by Step." *Portico*, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://www.portico.org/our-work/preservation-step-step/>.
- Portico. "Triggered Content." *Portico*, n.d. Accessed September 22, 2025. <https://www.portico.org/coverage/triggered-content/>.
- Romano, Frank. "E-Books and the Challenge of Preservation." *MFIR* 32, no. 1 (2003): 13–25. <https://doi.org/10.1515/MFIR.2003.13>.
- Skinner, Katherine, and Martin Halbert. "MetaArchive: A Cooperative Approach to Distributed Digital Preservation." *Against the Grain* 21, no. 1 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.7771/2380-176X.2489>.
- Smithers, Matt. "The Difference between a Repository/Platform with Backup and Preservation in an Archive Such as CLOCKSS." *CLOCKSS*, May 9, 2025. <https://clockss.org/difference-between-repository-and-archive/>.
- Smithers, Matt. "Web Archiving: The Process of Collecting and Storing Websites and Web Pages for Long-Term Access and Preservation." *CLOCKSS*, September 11, 2024. <https://clockss.org/web-archiving-the-process-of-collecting-and-storing-websites-and-web-pages-for-long-term-access-and-preservation/>.
- Stall, Shelley, Maryann E. Martone, Matthew Carson, et al. *Generalist Repository Comparison Chart*. October 8, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17315963>.
- Staring into the Void* | *Internet Archive Blogs*. December 25, 2024. <https://blog.archive.org/2024/12/25/staring-into-the-void/>.
- "The Keepers | The Keepers Registry." Accessed April 16, 2026. <https://keepers.issn.org/keepers>.

White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP). *Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research*. Executive Office of the President of the United States, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5479/10088/113528>.

Wikipedia. "Hachette v. Internet Archive." March 6, 2026. [https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Hachette v. Internet Archive&oldid=1342052660](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Hachette_v._Internet_Archive&oldid=1342052660).

Zenodo. "Data Preservation, Access, and Associated Timelines." Zenodo Documentation. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://help.zenodo.org/guides/nih/element4/>.

Zenodo. "FAQ Statistics." Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://zenodo.org/help/statistics>.

Zenodo. "Infrastructure." Zenodo, n.d. Accessed October 18, 2025. <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>.

"How Figshare.Com Meets the OSTP and NIH 'Desirable Characteristics for Data Repositories.'" *Figshare*, n.d. Accessed April 16, 2026. <https://info.figshare.com/user-guide/how-figshare-com-meets-the-ostp-and-nih-desirable-characteristics-for-data-repositories/>.

"What Is Amazon S3? - Amazon Simple Storage Service." Accessed April 16, 2026. <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/userguide/Welcome.html>.

"Archived Content." *CLOCKSS*, n.d. Accessed September 21, 2025. <https://clockss.org/whats-in-clockss/archived-content/>.